

TELEVISION ADVERTISING IMPACT ON FEMALE PRODUCT MARKETING IN SELECT NIGERIAN SCHOOLS: A CASE STUDY OF ALWAYS ULTRA

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Abstract: *This study is an arm of management which deals on product promotion. Product promotion is an effort by manufacturers to bring a particular product to the knowledge of the people who requires the product; this is otherwise known as market. This study specifically examined female product advertising through the use of the audio-visual broadcast media; the television. It deliberately chooses a female product that is required by all active females who by nature are expected to use the product. The study therefore examined the impact of television advertising using Always Ultra, a sanitary pad as a case study in selected Nigerian schools.*

The findings of the study indicated that over sixty per cent of respondents came in contact with the research specimen-Always Ultra through television advertisement. Therefore, if over sixty per cent of respondents came in contact with the product through television advertising, that means television advertising, that means television advertising is sixty per cent effective as a means of marketing female products in Nigeria in spite of social-economic and cultural values. It was recommended that television advertising should be used as a means to market female products in Nigeria. This is because, effective television advertising will yield sixty per cent of patronage by women as the minimum.

INTRODUCTION

A successful research work is as a result of a suitable research method adopted. Any research method could be used for any type of investigations for all situations, because there is no one research method that is peculiar to any investigation for all situations. While some investigations are best carried out in laboratories, others depend on direct observation, interview and questionnaire surveys.

Most researchers in Theatre and Media Arts use the survey research method. Depending on the nature of a particular research, a combination of different research procedures could be used to conduct a study. What is most important at the end of any research work does not entirely rely on the method used but on how effective such method can be in eliciting the needed research data. But if a researcher fails to use an appropriate research method, research will be unreliable.

RESEARCH QUESTION DESIGN

Data were retrieved via application of questionnaires, direct observation and interview. Questionnaires were administered to girls in school; this was supported with direct observation and interview. This evolved from the respondents the desired response on how effective television advertising is on product marketing. The questionnaires were designed to elicit yes or no answers or chose from a multiple option list of information applicable. Spaces were made available at the end of such list for any additional information included in the option box. Also a question was designed to allow

participants to freely express themselves, by writing a vivid description of Always Ultra advert they know.

PRODUCT MARKET SEGMENT

The product used to carry out this research is Always Ultra. And the product market segments are girls from Age Twelve (12) to women who are aged forty nine (49). For this reason the questionnaires were administered to girls in schools.

METHOD OF DATA COLLECTION

There are several ways of collecting data for research. And there are two major source of data collection; these are the primary and the secondary sources of data collection. The primary sources of data collection include the use of questionnaires, interview method and observation which include participant and non-participant observation. The secondary sources of data collection consist of the use of newspapers, magazines, textbooks, journals, seminar papers, internet sources etc.

For this research work, both primary and secondary sources of data collection were used. This is because the use of one source may not generate adequate and accurate data needed. Questionnaires were administered to respondents face to face. Open ended and closed forms of questions were used in the questionnaires. This was done to elicit adequate information. Open questions enable the respondents to give a more adequate presentation of his/her specific case. The open question possesses greater flexibility which may allow for greater validity. The closed questions were used also because they permit easier interpretation and tabulation.

Questionnaires were used because it has been known for its objectivity especially when the respondents are many. It is also very effective for retrieving data from a very large population within a period, aside this; information collected through the use of questionnaires can be more easily analyzed.

Direct observation helped the researcher to confirm what has been collected from the questionnaires. I carried out this observation by going to stores in Lagos and Ekpoma; this is known as non-participant observation. I had planned to interview the producer of the product used as a case study but I was denied the interview request. The secondary sources of data collection were consultation of journals, textbooks and internet sources.

METHOD OF DATA ANALYSIS

It is not always possible to make an observation on every individual whom a researcher had interest in. In this research work; the population in focus was so large that it was practically impossible to get them all. Hence, due to restrictions such as population size, time, financial costs etc. I decided to adopt sampling method, random sampling in particular rather than study the entire population. This is because it conserves time and also effectively represents certain elements that would have been underplayed using other procedures.

According to the Oxford Advanced Learners dictionary 7th Edition, sample is a number of people or things taken from a larger group and used in tests to provide information about the group. In this regard three schools were selected for this study two (2) in Lagos state and One (1) in Edo state. The total questionnaires that were administered were one hundred and fifty (150). The respondents were girls. Fifty (50) questionnaires were distributed to each school.

Eva Adelaja Senior Girls Secondary school – 50

Gulf Flower High School – 50

DATA ANALYSIS

Section A

Ambrose Alli University – 50

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

According to Slater data collected during research must be collated, coded and analyzed to make it meaningful (22). He further emphasized that a good analysis should give the feel and flavor of the situation studied in-depth, which calls for careful interpretation of data retrieved and “artistic” presentation skill so as to communicate the findings. A good analysis must be responsive to the research questions and purpose, in the sense that, research objectives must be the pillar which the research depends on.

This chapter presents and analyses the data retrieved in the course of the study. The data were collected via the use of questionnaires, which were responded to by girls who are students of Eva Adelaja Senior Girls Secondary School, Gulf Flower High School and Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma. For the purpose of clarity, all questions are analyzed. For data calculation, simple percentage and frequency counts are used. While for illustration, tables are used

$$\frac{N}{TN} \times \frac{100}{1}$$

N = Number of respondents

TN = Total number of respondents

General information

Out of Fifty (50) questionnaires that were given to Eva Adelaja Senior Girls secondary school, fifty (50) were returned answered. That of Gulf Flower High School, fifty (50) questionnaires were administered to them and the fifty (50) were returned answered. While thirty eight (38) questionnaires were received answered out of fifty (50) questionnaires that were distributed to Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma. The total number of questionnaires distributed were One hundred and fifty (150), out of which a total number of One hundred and thirty eight (138) were received answered.

Table 1: Sex distribution of respondents

Variable	Frequency	%
Male	-	-
Female	138	100
Total	138	100

This table indicates that 138 (100%) of the respondents were female. This shows that the questionnaires were only met for females

Section B

Table 2: Do you watch television?

	EVA ADELAJA	%	GULF FLOWER	%	A.A.U.E	%
Yes	50	100	50	100	38	100
No	-	-	-	-	-	-
Total	50	100	50	100	38	100

The table above indicates that most people watch television. From Eva Adelaja 50(100%) respondents watch television, while from Gulf Flower 50 (100%) respondents watch television and also from A.A.U.E 38 (100%) respondent watch television.

Table 3: When do you watch television?

	EVA ADELAJA	%	GULF FLOWER	%	A.A.U.E	%
Morning	1	2	1	3	1	2.2
Afternoon	6	12.2	3	9	13	28.3
Evening	42	85.7	30	88	32	69.6
Total	49	100	34	100	46	100

Table 3 above shows when respondents watch television. From Eva Adelaja 1(2%), Gulf Flower 1 (3%) and A.A.U.E 1(2.2%) watch television in the morning. Respondents who watch television in the afternoon, from Eva Adelaja 6 (12.2%), Gulf Flower 3 (9%), A.A.U.E 13 (28.3%). While respondents who watch television in the evening from Eva Adelaja it was 42 (85.7%), Gulf Flower was 30(88%) and A.A.U.E 32(69.7%).

Table 4: Do you watch commercials?

	EVA ADELAJA	%	GULF FLOWER	%	A.A.U.E	%
Yes	26	53.1	18	36	24	64.9
No	3	6.1	3	6	-	-
Sometimes	20	40.8	29	58	13	35.1
Total	49	100	50	100	37	100

The table above shows the attitude of respondents towards watching commercials. From Eva Adelaja 26(53.1%), Gulf Flower 18(36%), while A.A.U.E 24(64.9%) watch commercials. The percentage of respondents that watch commercials sometimes are viz, Eva Adelaja 20(40.8%) Gulf Flower 29(58%), and A.A.U.E 13(35.1%) while very few respondent like Eva Adelaja 3(6.1%) Gulf Flower 3(6%), do not watch commercial.

Table 5: Between television advert and radio advert which do you prefer or like

	EVA ADELAJA	%	GULF FLOWER	%	A.A.U.E	%
Television	47	94	49	98	37	97.4
Radio	3	6	1	2	-	-
None of the above	-	-	-	-	1	2.6
Total	50	100	50	100	38	100

Table 5 above indicates the means of advert that is most preferred by respondents from Eva Adelaja 47(94%), Gulf Flower 49(98%), and A.A.U.E 37(97.4%), preferred television advert. While few respondents like Eva Adelaja 3(6%) and Gulf Flower 1(2%) like radio advert. But only 1(2.6%) from A.A.U.E liked neither.

Table 6: Do you know *Always Ultra*?

	EVA ADELAJA	%	GULF FLOWER	%	A.A.U.E	%
Yes	49	98	47	95.9	38	100
No	-	-	2	4.1	-	-
Not sure	1	2	-	-	-	-

Total	50	100	49	100	38	100
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As indicated in table 6 above almost all the respondents from Eva Adelaja 49(98%), Gulf Flower 47(95.9%) and A.A.U.E 38 (100%) knows *Always Ultra*. While 2(4.1%) from Gulf Flower do not know *Always Ultra*. But only 1(2%) respondent from Eva Adelaja seems not to be sure.

Table 7: How did you get to know *Always Ultra*, through?

	EVA ADELAJA	%	GULF FLOWER	%	A.A.U.E	%
Television	48	96	49	100	38	100
Radio	1	2	-	-	-	-
Newspaper	1	2	-	-	-	-
Total	50	100	49	100	38	100

From the table above, the statistic shows that almost all the respondents from Eva Adelaja 48(96%), Gulf Flower 49(100%) and A.A.U.E 38(100%) got to know *Always Ultra* through Television. While 1(2%) from Eva Adelaja got to know *Always Ultra* from radio and also 1(2%) from Eva Adelaja knows *Always Ultra* through newspaper.

Table 8: What kind of sanitary pad do you use?

	EVA ADELAJA	%	GULF FLOWER	%	A.A.U.E	%
<i>Always</i>	36	72	34	81	36	94.7
Lady care	13	26	6	14.3	1	2.6
Everyday	1	2	2	4.8	1	2.6
Total	50	100	42	100	38	100

The table above shows the kind of sanitary pad used by the respondents. From Eva Adelaja 36(72%), Gulf Flower 34(81%) and A.A.U.E 36(94.7%) use *Always Ultra*. While respondents that use lady care are viz, Eva Adelaja 13(26%), Gulf Flower, 6(14.3%) A.A.U.E, 1(2%). Only few respondents from Eva Adelaja 1(2%), Gulf Flower 2(4.8%) and A.A.U.E 1(2.6%) use everyday.

Table 9: What motivated you into using any of the products chosen above?

	EVA ADELAJA	%	GULF FLOWER	%	A.A.U.E	%
Television advert	41	82	37	82.2	34	89.5
Radio advert	1	2	-	-	-	-
Newspaper	1	2	-	-	-	-
Specify other	7	14	8	17.8	4	10.5
Total	50	100	45	100	38	100

Table 9 above shows the factors that motivated respondents into using the kind of sanitary pad they use. From Eva Adelaja 41(82%), Gulf Flower 37(82.2%) and A.A.U.E 34(89.5%), were motivated by television advert. While few respondents from Eva Adelaja, 7(14%), Gulf Flower 8(17.8%) and A.A.U.E 4(10.5%), were motivated by other means. But very few respondents from Eva Adelaja 1(2%) were motivated by radio and newspaper advert.

Table 10: How did you learn how to use pad?

	EVA ADELAJA	%	GULF FLOWER	%	A.A.U.E	%
From television advert	29	58	21	47.7	21	55.3
From radio advert	1	2	-	-	-	-
From newspaper advert	-	-	-	-	1	2.6
Specify other	20	40	23	52.3	16	42.1
Total	50	100	44	100	38	100

Table 10 above indicates that television is the best medium that can be used to show illustration of goods or service. From Eva Adelaja, 29(58%), Gulf Flower, 21 (47.7%) and A.A.U.E, 21 (55.3%), learned how to use pad from television advert. While 20(40%) from Eva Adelaja, 23(52.2%) from Gulf Flower, and 16(42.1%) from A.A.U.E got to learn how to use

pad from other means. But only 1(2%) from Eva Adelaja got to know how to use pad from radio advert and only 1(2.6) from A.A.U.E learned to use pad from newspaper

Table 11: What do you think about *Always Ultra* television advert?

	EVA ADELAJA	%	GULF FLOWER	%	A.A.U.E	%
Good/captivating	47	95.9	43	91.5	35	92.1
Boring/bad	1	2.0	2	4.3	1	2.6
Not sure	1	2.0	2	4.3	2	5.3
Total	49	100	47	100	38	100

The table above shows how creative an advert is. From Eva Adelaja 47(95.9%), Gulf Flower 43(91.5%) and AAUE 35(92.1%) all agreed that *Always Ultra* advert is good. But respondents that disagreed that *Always Ultra* advert is good are viz, Eva Adelaja 1(2%), Gulf Flower 2(4.3%), A.A.U.E 1(2.6%). While 1(2%) from Eva Adelaja, 2(4.3%) from Gulf Flower and A.A.U.E 2(5.3%) were indecisive.

Table 12: Do you like the way they dramatize their television advert?

	EVA ADELAJA	%	GULF FLOWER	%	A.A.U.E	%
Yes	49	98	49	100	38	100
No	1	2	-	-	-	-
Total	50	100	49	100	38	100

As indicated in table 12 above, statistics shows that respondents from Eva Adelaja 49(98%), Gulf Flower 49(100%) and AAUE 38(100%) likes the way *Always Ultra* dramatized their advert. While only 1(2%) from Eva Adelaja dislikes the way *Always Ultra* dramatize their advert.

Table 13: Can you remember any of the *Always Ultra* television adverts you like? Indicate by writing a vivid description of it.

	EVA ADELAJA	%	GULF FLOWER	%	A.A.U.E	%
Check, check	6	12	11	22	13	34.2
Eight hours long	38	76	28	56	10	26.3
No stain	-	-	2	4	4	10
Nothing	6	12	9	18	11	29
Total	50	100	50	100	38	100

The above table indicates that respondents remember an advert that is creative and most especially an advert that is accompanied with music or song. From Eva Adelaja 6(12%), Gulf Flower 1(22%), and A.A.U.E 13(34.2) wrote about "check check" advert. While from Eva Adelaja 38(76%), Gulf Flower 28(56%), A.A.U.E 10(26.3%) wrote on "Eight hours long" advert and very few respondents from Gulf Flower 2(4%) and A.A.U.E 4(10.5%) wrote on "no stain" advert. But 6(12%) from Eva Adelaja 9(18%) from Gulf Flower and 11(29%) from A.A.U.E wrote nothing.

RESULT OF ANALYZED DATA

Results generated from the data analysis shows that most people prefer television advert to any other medium used to advertise goods, ideas or services. It shows that almost everybody watch and have a television set. From the result analysis, it was revealed that most people got to know the product they use from television advert. The result shows that people like television advert. And they also like advert that is creative and dramatized. The result also shows that television is the best medium that can be used to describe a product, good or service.

SUMMARY

This work examines the impact of television advertising on product marketing using *Always Ultra* as a case study. This was initiated by the desire to determine the impact television advert has on marketing a product. From the introduction and the review of this research, it was observed that people like pictures more than words and that picture or motion pictures are the best to use in show casing your product or service. The research further shows the role television has on the economy and how it can be used for marketing of products and services. It goes further to that show that television is the best medium that can be used to give adequate information about a product, service, or idea. Aside television advertising, the study also talks or gives little information about newspaper advertising, radio

advertising outdoor advertising, direct mail advertising etc. The research did not fail to talk about the efficiency of drama in advertising.

The total sample population of this study was one hundred and fifty (150); which were girls. Questionnaires, observation method and consultation of relevant literature were used to collect the data for this research work. Simple percentage methods were used in analyzing the data, statistical table were effectively used for illustration.

The study revealed that people watch television, most especially in the evenings. It also revealed that people prefer television advert to any other medium. The study revealed that most persons were motivated to use the product they use from television advert.

The study also reveals that people like an advert that is being dramatized and accompanied with music. The study also shows that the product *Always Ultra* is used by many girls because of the advert they saw on television, which gives *Always Ultra* an edge over all other sanitary pads.

CONCLUSION

The collection of various information concerning television advertising from different schools in Lagos and Edo state (Eva Adelaja Senior Girls Secondary School, Gulf Flower High School and Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma) shows that television advertising has a great impact on product marketing. This is because people watch television and most times watch commercials (See table 2&4)

Dramas in adverting along side with music are factors that attract the audience. Majority of the respondents affirm this (see table 11, 12 & 13). It was because of this drama, music; creativity that most girls were able to give vivid description of *Always Ultra* advert. And most of them wrote on “check check” advert and “eight hours long” advert because of the drama and music inherent in the advert. The advert of *Always Ultra* on television made many girls to patronize *Always Ultra* (see table 7, 8 and 9). Television advertising also helps give description of product (see table 10). The introduction of drama and songs in advertising makes people like commercials (see table 12)

RECOMMENDATION

For maximum utilization of television advertising, advertisers should first seek for a good advert agent to help then in doing a good advert. The advert should also be creative and contain music or phrase that will attract the audience. Advertisers should identify their market

target and place their advert on air when they know that their target audiences are likely to watch television. Advert should be repeated as often as possible so as to retain potential consumers. Because when you stop advertising your product, service or idea for some time people thinks it no longer exist. So you must continuously advertise your product.

Most importantly, if you must advertise your product, idea or service; avoid doing a short commercial that will last for 30 seconds, because firstly, it will hardly be noticed by the audience and secondly the audience will hardly get the information you are trying to convey.

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